

Poster presentation**Effect of surface properties of the lake ramparts on the local lake breeze****Enora Moisan, Audrey Chatain, Scot Rafkin, Alejandro Soto, Shannon MacKenzie**

The atmospheric circulation above Titan's lakes and the exchange of mass and energy between the atmosphere and the lakes are still poorly constrained. Yet, these are important for quantitatively describing the global volatile cycle, and for interpreting radar and specular reflection signals from the lakes. Understanding the wind circulation and methane cycle at the local scale is essential to prepare future exploration missions to Titan, like the Dragonfly drone.

The Cassini-Huygens mission showed that Titan's hydrocarbon lakes are located around the poles and have two main morphologies: some are wide with complex shorelines and diameters up to several hundred kilometers, while others are small lakes with diameters of a few tens of kilometers, surrounded by sharp edges and high topography terrains ("ramparts"). Lakes with ramparts are called "sharp-edged depressions" (SED). The ramparts surrounding these lakes can have different surface properties from the rest of the land, which influences the energy fluxes between the surface and the atmosphere. Thus, the local wind circulation in the planetary boundary layer can be changed around the SED lakes, as well as the air and surface temperatures, and the methane cycle.

To investigate and quantify this effect, we use a 2D mesoscale atmospheric model adapted to Titan from the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model used for Earth (mtWRF: Rafkin and Soto 2020, Chatain et al. 2022). We use a 1200 km wide and 15 km high domain, with a 1 km horizontal grid length and 50 vertical layers. In the middle of the domain, we position a lake of 20 km of diameter, surrounded on each side by 5 km of terrain with different surface properties compared to the rest of the land. We study the effect of varying thermal inertia, surface roughness length, emissivity and albedo on the local lake breeze.

We find that the surface roughness length has a significant effect on the winds, the surface temperature and the methane fluxes (for a higher roughness: slower horizontal winds, less methane evaporation, and higher surface temperatures on the lake borders and the ramparts). Surface emissivity and albedo influence the radiative fluxes, but have only a moderate impact on the winds, the temperature and the methane fluxes. Finally, the thermal inertia has only a minor effect. These results therefore indicate that the current uncertainties from the observations on thermal inertia, emissivity and albedo of terrains do not affect our lake breeze results, which is not the case for the surface roughness.

We are currently adding topography into the model, an important missing property of the ramparts surrounding SED lakes. We expect the addition of rampart topography to have a significant impact on the wind circulation and on the methane cycle.